

AS A NON-LEGACY CUTTING PROCESS: ABRASIVE WATER JET (AWJ) APPLICATIONS IN THE AVIATION INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

There are some conventional cutting techniques but Abrasive Water Jet (AWJ) is a modern one. It has been increasingly using in the industry since the 1980s. AWJ cutting process allows cutting of various materials, from soft materials to brittle materials, from ceramic materials to composite materials and it has quickly become a part of non-legacy cutting methods. The aforementioned material types are used not only for airborne parts but follow-on-support phase parts also. Aircraft fly “only” with airworthy parts and components and it requires very stiff manufacturing systematic. Because of its competitive environment and high technology, the aviation industry requires a fast, precise and cost-effective production process. Airworthy part design and production processes are clearly described by national and international aviation authorities. The reason why AWJ rapidly gaining a place within the aviation industry is that the material cutting efficiency is high and most of the time there is no need for secondary operations after cutting. Therewithal, the analyses performed during and after cutting demonstrate that the Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) does not occur. Also, not occurring of thermal load is accepted as one of the advantages of AWJ. In this study, the information related to the usage of AWJ cutting technology which provides many advantages in the aviation industry will be submitted. The projections for commercial aircraft manufacturing in the next 20 years have been included in the study also. In this way, it is aimed to create situational awareness for the employees of industrial companies and academicians.

Keywords: Abrasive Water Jet (AWJ), Aviation Industry, Airworthiness, Aircraft,

1. INTRODUCTION

It is a well-known issue that the aviation industry has been actively pioneering the usage of advanced materials and modern manufacturing techniques. Reducing the weight is an important objective. The lighter aircraft means, less fuel burning, the ability of higher payloads carrying and longer ranges. This made aviation industry to focus on improving new technologies. Although usage of Abrasive Water Jet (AWJ) had started before aviation industry in 1830's, it developed itself rapidly and found a large field in aerospace. In the beginning there were some conventional cutting processes like sawing, machining etc. In time the requirements have changed in accordance with the aviation industry. Now AWJ is accepted as one of the most advanced cutting technologies [1]. On the other hand, the aircraft part and component manufacturers are in a dense competition environment and they are forced to produce more complex parts, with more reasonable prices. Aviation industry is rapidly growing. A case study by Airbus et al shows that [2] the airline traffic doubles every 15 years. The AVIATION industry is a strategic high-tech industry which reflects a country's overall technological robustness and the overall industrial level [3].

2. RESEARCH STATUS

In this study information about advanced materials and modern manufacturing methods which are used in aviation industry will be provided while monitoring the aircraft manufacturing market with numbers.

Surface roughness is an issue and narrow-tolerances are necessary in aviation industry that's why AWJ is a must especially for large scale structural parts.

2.1. AWJ HISTORY AND INTERACTIONS

Usage of AWJ goes to the beginning of 19th century. At that time AWJ was used by Russian engineers especially for mining activities [4]. After mining, AWJ has found a large field for other cutting operations. In the aviation industry, the materials which are used for airborne parts are quite expensive. and for those parts mechanic loads and thermal loads are not wanted. Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) is an unwelcome phenomenon which affects the “not-cheap aviation grade material’s crystal structure”. While cutting the materials with AWJ, there’s no thermal loads and mechanic loads [5]. If the material has a thick section or requires ‘no HAZ’ or is made from copper or a similar material that is highly reflective to some laser wavelengths, then AWJ may be more suitable cutting technique [6]. With the optimization of cutting parameters, the surface quality could be better. A case study by Saraçyakupoğlu T., et al [7] shows that optimization of the pressure, cutting velocity and diameter of water jet, effects the quality of surface. This optimization for BS 7191 355 EMZ and ASTM A516 Gr.60 steels is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Comparison of BS 7191 355 EMZ and ASTM A516 Gr.60 Steels [7]

With general description, decreasing the cutting velocity increases the surface quality [8]. Figure 2. shows the interactions amongst the abrasive particle, AWJ and material.

Figure 2. Interactions of AWJ Process [9]

Considering the surface quality, it is observed that AWJ provides more sensitive surface comparing with cutting with gas and cutting with plasma as it is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Comparison of AWJ with Other Cutting Techniques [10]

2.2. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF AWJ

Advantages:

- Distortions are neglectable,
- HAZ is almost zero or insignificant,
- One cutting tool for cutting different types of materials and thicknesses,
- Ability to cut very thick materials (over 300 mm),
- A very small amount of loss material (It is very important for expensive aviation grade materials),
- Short machine setup times,
- Generally, no need to change the nozzle,
- Easy automation,
- Water and abrasive material (generally garnet) are environmental friendly materials,

- Reuse of the abrasive material (up to 80% is possible),
- No impurities like grease, oil, and emulsions,
- No dust (Dust goes to water at the bottom of the table)
- An ignorable tiny mist is generated in the cutting area.

Disadvantages:

- Constraints of machining 3D shapes,
- High-speed linear cutting gets an unwanted “V” profile,
- At high-speed cutting of circles and arches, waterjet may deviate,
- At high-speed cutting of inner angles waterjet may produce notches,
- During cutting of thick materials striations may occur along with the depth of the cut due to high transverse speed or insufficient pressure,
- Cutting of very hard materials is difficult,
- After cutting operation, corrosion sensitive materials need to be protected [11].

With the benefit of advantages and capability of high-quality surface, AWJ has found a vast usage in the aviation industry. Cutting of large composite materials, as well as metallic ones, makes AWJ a popular technique. Machining the large parts like wing, tail and skin parts on the aircraft is a trend requisition of enlarging aviation industry. Boeing which is a leading aircraft manufacturing company makes 5-axis AWJ machine a standard machine because during the cutting operation, AWJ, prevents delamination, splitting and edge scratches [12]. During the production phase, each part and component must be carefully machined to the highest possible quality, as even the slightest error or structural weakness could lead to serious accidents or incidents [13].

3. AIRCRAFT PRODUCERS AND THEIR MARKET VOLUMES AT THE GLOBAL SCALE

Manufacturing a part or component in accordance with the regulations of airworthiness authorities is called as ‘manufacturing of flight-ready’ part or component. It is an airborne part or component. Having this capability only possible by passing successfully meticulous audits of the airworthiness authorities. Having Product Organization Approval (POA) means Part 21 certification. With the recent market reports, the aircraft manufacturers that dominate the global aviation market which have POA accreditations are the companies such as Boeing (US), Airbus (European Union), COMAC (China-Russian), Bombardier (Canada), Embraer (Brazil), ATR (France) and some others. The growth of the aviation market can be seen in the reports submitted by these companies. These companies and expected incomes for the period of ‘2017-2037’ is given below;

- Boeing will manufacture 42,730 (Forty-Two Thousand Seven Hundred and Thirty) aircraft with the total price of 6,300,000,000,000 (Six Trillion Three Hundred Billion) US \$ [14],
- Airbus will manufacture 37,400 (Thirty-Seven Thousand Four Hundred) aircraft in with the total price of 5,800,000,000,000 (Five Trillion Eight Hundred Billion) US \$ [15],
- Comac will manufacture 41,850 (Forty-One Thousand Eight Hundred and Fifty) aircraft with the total price of 5,746,000,000,000 (Five Trillion Seven Hundred and Forty-Six Billion) US \$ [16],
- Bombardier will manufacture 12,550 (Twelve Thousand Five Hundred and Fifty) aircraft with the total price of 820,000,000,000 (Eight Hundred and Twenty Billions) US \$ [17],
- Embraer will manufacture 10,550 (Ten Thousand Five Hundred and Fifty) aircraft with the total price of 600,000,000,000 (Six Hundred Billion) US \$ [18],

- ATR will manufacture 3.020 (Three Thousand and Twenty) aircraft with the total price of 200,000,000,000 (Two Hundred Billion) US \$ [19].

In the general evaluation, approximately 142,400 passenger aircraft will be produced between years of 2017-2037 and the estimated market size is 19,430,000,000,000 US \$ (Nineteen Trillion Four Hundred and Thirty Billion). These projections are only four manufacturing stage and don't include the follow-on-support phase. This huge market makes mandatory of having 'certified sub-contractors' in the aviation industry. The companies which hold POA certifications audit their sub-contractors such as AWJ companies with the stiff rules and regulations of airworthiness authorities.

4. CUTTING PROCESS OF MATERIALS LIKE COMPOSITE AND ALUMINUM IN AVIATION INDUSTRY

Pioneering the novel technologies is a must in the aviation industry because the market is huge and competition is stringent. What aviation industry was doing decades ago has now become a regular application for other industries like automotive, whitegoods etc. For example, the aviation industry was the earliest adopter of carbon fiber materials, and it was the first to integrate Computer Aided Design (CAD) / Computer Aided Manufacturing (CAM) into its design process [20]. Since the competition is stringent reducing the flight operation cost is an important objective of airliner companies. The reduction of 1 kg built-in aircraft weight is able to reduce carbon emissions by 0.94 kg for the case of the Boeing 747-400 which has maximum-take-off-weight is 396,890 kg and by 0.475 kg in the Airbus A330-300 which has maximum-take-off-weight is 242,000 kg. Also, it was stated that a reduction of 1 kg of carbon emissions can also save up to 0.3 kg of aviation fuel [21]. It means a lot in the name of operational cost. Weight optimization is possible with the usage of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) materials. The density of polymer composites typically half of the weight of aluminum and one-fifth of that of steel [22]. Evolving the parts from aluminum or steel to polymers reduces the operational cost. Leader aircraft manufacturer companies like Boeing and Airbus are focusing on material change. In Figure 3, the material spectrum of Boeing 787 Dreamliner is shown.

Figure 4. Materials Used in Boeing 787 Dreamliner [23]

Using composite materials in Boeing 767 is even higher than Boeing 787 Dreamliner with the percentage of 77% [12]. In Figure 5 it is shown that composite materials which are used for Airbus A350 XWB about 53%.

Figure 5. Materials Used in Airbus A350 XWB [24]

The parts which are used in above-mentioned aircrafts vary in size from large parts such as bulkheads, longerons, supports, wings and fuselage sections to small size parts such as brackets, clips, and door stringers. AWJ is the most suitable cutting methodology for having the parts to End-of-Part (EOP) borderline [25]. For example, Airbus A310’s vertical stabilizer (8,3 m. high by 7,8 m. wide at the base) a major aerodynamic and structural member fabricated in its entirety from carbon composite with a total weight saving of almost 400 kg when compared with the Al alloy material previously used. Besides, the CFRP fin box comprises only 95 parts excluding fasteners, compared with 2076 parts in the metal unit [26]. Another important AWJ in the aviation industry is cutting of honeycomb materials which are too fragile for cutting using with CNC machining cutters. Since low forces applied to the workpiece during machining, AWJ enables fragile materials to be cut without distortion or breakage [27]. Cutting velocity is very important during the cutting process of CFRP with AWJ. In figure 6 it is shown that unsatisfactory cutting happens as the velocity is lower or higher than the optimum value.

Figure 6. Sections with Lower or Higher of Optimum Value of Velocity [28].

5. CONCLUSION

In accordance with the United Nations International Civil Aviation Organization’s 2016 capacity and efficiency report, global air traffic has doubled in size once every 15 years since 1977 and will continue to do so [29]. This traffic makes the aviation industry a field of ‘hard

game'. Growing in manufacturing market forces companies to manufacture parts faster, more precise and more cost-effective.

Because of the demand for lowering the operations costs, weight reduction studies will always be while maintaining the strength properties of the materials. The lighter aircraft means cheaper operational costs and lower CO² emissions. That's why in the future the parts will be exchanged with the lighter ones as soon as they meet the safety requirements. At that point AWJ will be used in the aviation industry for large scale or small size parts which are used with lighter materials like CFRP, polymers, aluminum alloys etc. Optimization of pressure, cutting velocity and water jet diameter gives opportunities to have more precise surfaces. While bringing the borders of the parts to EOP, AWJ is the most suitable cutting process since the wastage is almost ignorable and surface quality is high.

AWJ, is a mature process being used safely in the aviation industry and it will be a subject which grows rapidly at the global level.

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